

METHODS FOR PROPER TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION WHEN TRANSPORTING PERISHABLE GOODS IN REFRIGERATED CONTAINERS

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АННОТАЦИЯ В этой статье рассматривается использование рефконтейнеров с регулируемой температурой при транспортировке скоропортящихся грузов. Основными факторами выбора правильного типа оборудования являются размер и вес перевозимого груза, характер перевозки и выбор необходимой температуры. В рефконтейнерах предотвращает попадание воздуха в грузовой отсек сверху. Учитывая, что количество, размер и расположение отверстий в контейнерах различаются в зависимости от продукта, приведены методы оптимального размещения транспортных тар в предлагаемых размерах.

Ключевые слова: доставка, рефконтейнер, скоропортящиеся грузы, холодильная техника, транспортная цепочка, грузоотправитель, получатель.

ANNOTATION This article discusses the use of temperature-controlled refrigerated containers for the transportation of perishable goods. The main factors in choosing the right type of equipment are the size and weight of the cargo being transported, the nature of transportation and the choice of the required temperature. In refrigerated containers, it prevents air from entering the cargo compartment from above. Considering that the number, size and location of holes in containers vary depending on the product, the methods of optimal placement of transport containers in the proposed sizes are given.

Keywords: delivery, refrigerated container, perishable loads, refrigeration equipment, transport chain, shipper, recipient.

Introduction

Refrigerated containers first appeared in the 1960s as examples of refrigerated shipping containers. Cooling was provided via a central refrigeration unit connected by a pipe or air duct to the container, leading to these containers being called "porthole" containers. As the name implies, these containers had built-in refrigeration units and only required a power source to operate. These containers became widely used across various sectors and quickly became the standard for transporting goods along new trade routes due to their convenience.

Traditional refrigerated containers operate within a temperature range of -30°C to 30°C (-22°F to 86°F), which was not always adequate for maintaining and evenly distributing the required temperatures for perishables. This limitation led to the development of specialized temperature-controlled containers designed to maintain and evenly distribute temperatures to protect shipments, such as vegetables and other perishable goods.

Modern refrigerated containers can lower the temperature within a specific timeframe, but for intermodal transportation, they are generally designed to maintain a pre-set temperature rather than actively reduce it. The main types of goods transported in refrigerated containers include fruits, vegetables, fish, meat, and poultry. However, many other products, including flowers and pharmaceuticals, are also shipped in these containers.

Shippers or receivers may require that the goods be transported under active cooling conditions throughout the delivery chain, meaning the equipment must remain continuously connected to a power source. For this purpose, it is crucial that the container can be equipped with a mobile generator (gen-set). Active cooling is necessary for routes with high average ambient temperatures. On some trade routes, refrigerated containers may be transported with the refrigeration system turned off, as an alternative to transporting empty containers. Intermodal operators need to be aware of this practice since transporting other types of cargo in these containers

could damage the equipment, leading to inefficiencies or the risk of contaminating subsequent shipments.

Figure 1. Possible method of semi-air circulation in a two-compartment refrigerated container

The main factors in selecting the appropriate type of equipment are the volume and weight of the cargo being transported, the nature of the transportation, and the required temperature. Standard refrigerated containers typically come in lengths of 20, 40, or 45 feet and heights of either 8 feet 6 inches or 9 feet 6 inches (the latter known as "High Cube" or HC containers). However, 45-foot refrigerated containers are quite rare globally and are mainly used for national and regional transport . Currently, the majority of the world's container fleet consists of 40-foot HC containers (see Table 1).

Table 1

Types of Refrigerated Containers Used

Types	Name	Size	Carrying capacity
45R1	High 40 fut	67-68 m ³	29,9-30,5 t 65918-67240 fut
42R1	Normal 40 fut	56 m ³	28,5 t 62831 fut
22R1	Normal 20 fut	29 m ³	26-27,5 t 57320-60627 fut

The standardization of refrigerated containers (refcontainers) was related to the desire to optimize their performance and make more efficient use of space on board. Trailers, on the other hand, can vary significantly in size and load capacity, as their maximum dimensions are determined by national and international weight, axle load, and dimension restrictions, which must comply with road traffic safety legislation in the countries where the trailers are used.

On all trade routes, refcontainers, equipped and serviced according to the needs for transporting vegetables and melons, are offered. Below is a list of options for use:

- Having some forms of equipment monitoring to provide current information on the operation of the transport vehicle. However, some vendors may offer additional tools for remote monitoring of temperature and condition, which could be beneficial for the shipper or receiver;
- Special refrigeration for quality maintenance during the journey (e.g., controlling the product's temperature);
- Specialized dual-sided refrigeration devices, especially useful for transporting sensitive chemicals and pharmaceutical products;
- Air circulation (ripening) for fruits and vegetables, controlled by an air-regulated atmosphere to extend their shelf life. This reduces the risk of cargo damage and mold growth.

In transporting vegetable products, it is necessary to ensure that the refcontainer's capacity and refrigeration equipment meet the following conditions:

- The refcontainer equipment is in good condition, with no physical damage;
- All components required for the operation of the equipment are present;
- The refcontainer is very clean, with no signs of mold, plants, pests, or other species;
- All residues from previously transported cargo, old labels, and hazard signs are removed;

- Refrigeration and lubrication devices are adequately supplied;
- Condenser drain pipes are clean.

According to the proposed model, the operator is responsible for ensuring that the provided refcontainer is clean and free from cargo residues, hazardous materials, plants, plant products, and visible pests. The general design features of the refcontainer, including joints between wall coverings, may make cleaning difficult.

If air circulation is insufficient, even if the refrigeration unit operates correctly and provides the correct cooling level, there is a risk that the proper temperature will not be maintained throughout the entire cargo volume. Additionally, the accumulation of ripening gases can lead to rapid ripening of the cargo, reducing its shelf life and increasing the risk of mold and decay. Refrigerated cargo can generate its own heat, so ensuring adequate air circulation through the package is essential.

Packaging requirements for refrigerated or fresh cargo vary depending on whether a refrigerated trailer or refcontainer is planned to be used, as the airflow inside them moves differently.

Figure 2. Proposed ventilated box

For all refrigerated containers used for rail transportation, as they draw air from the bottom (upward airflow), for loading fresh fruits and vegetables in refrigerated containers, there should be ventilation ducts both at the top and bottom, so that when the boxes are stacked, the ducts align with each other. The number, size, and positioning of the ducts in the containers vary depending on the product.

Figure 3. Air circulation in stacking boxes

For all refrigerated containers, air flows from top to bottom, driven primarily by the horizontal movement of the air current. Therefore, there should be ventilation ducts on the sides of the packages containing fresh fruits and vegetables to be loaded in refrigerated containers. When the boxes are stacked, aligned ducts facilitate horizontal channels for air movement through the cargo mass. The number, volume, and positioning of ducts in the containers vary depending on the product. If crossbars are used for stacking and securely fastened, and if pallets are used for transporting refrigerated cargo, it is necessary to ensure sufficient ventilation of the crossbars and proper attachment of the pallet to the crossbar. Avoiding the use of crossbars is necessary as they obstruct airflow. Refrigerated goods need to be pre-cooled before loading since ventilation ducts in the boxes are not required during loading due to the absence of heat or gases generated. The package should be pre-cooled to the required loading temperature. Boxes should be stacked directly on top of each other in a tight block formation, ensuring no gaps between boxes or pallets. Blocking

airflow from the block is reasonable as it helps maintain the overall temperature of the cargo's main portion. Guidelines for loading refrigerated containers specify that if refrigerated containers are used, the cargo space should be evenly distributed throughout the entire container to ensure the most efficient airflow. [8,9,10,11]

Transport package and refrigerated container parameters are presented in the form of interdependent mathematical models. An algorithm has been developed to determine the rational packing of refrigerated containers. The method of optimization is employed. The practical significance of the work lies in increasing the transport batch size of fruits and vegetable products. The concept of cargo volume refers to the change in cargo quantity from one point to another in a year. The total number of transported goods is calculated based solely on the volume of goods in one parameter.

Determining cargo volume involves understanding the object's direction from one point to another. These parameters can be modified to several extents. Depending on its nature, cargo volume can be periodic or continuous, inbound or outbound, simple or complex, outgoing or incoming, internal or external, producing, consuming, distributing, and others.

The characteristics of cargo volume are based on the following main parameters:

- The total number of cargoes moved over a period Q (for a year - annual cargo turnover, t/year ; for a month - monthly cargo turnover, t/month ; for a day - daily; intensity λ , t/hour or units/hour);
- The size of the cargo batch Q_1, Q_2, \dots, t , units;
- The average size of the cargo batch Q , t , units;
- The number of cargo names in the cargo batch $p_1 p_2, \dots$;
- The average number of cargo naming in the cargo batch p ;
- The number of cargo spaces in the cargo batch $N_1 N_2 \dots$;
- The average number of cargo spaces in the cargo batch N ;

- The types and schemes of cargo transportation (bulk cargo, containers), trailers and platforms;
- Dimensions (width, length, height), mm, and weight gross and net, kg of individual cargo;
- The time of sending or receiving the cargo batch t_1, t_2, \dots ;
- The interval between sending and receiving the cargo batch $\Delta t_1, \Delta t_2$;
- The average interval between sending and receiving the cargo batch Δt .

The total value of cargo turnover in one year:

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \quad (1)$$

Here, Q_i -represents the mass of the i -th transport batch, t ;
 n -represents the number of transport batches in one year.

So, to efficiently organize and optimize the total volume of cargo turnover, we first need to select the parameters of the transport batch based on standard considerations, and then understand the reloading of cargo on board based on technology.

Optimizing and organizing cargo turnover means first selecting the cargo itself and its parameters efficiently. It is crucial to choose the most appropriate criteria, which include the types of cargo in the individual transport parameter, the dimensions of the transport batch, and others.

The volume of the transport batch q_t and the cargo carrying capacity q_v characterize the transport vehicle's ability to carry cargo. For instance, the cargo carrying capacity is utilized in our task concerning the swaying of refrigerated wagons, the volume of fruits and vegetables γ , the suitability of the wagon design for transporting goods, the use of technical means, the characteristics of cargo and packaging in transport, and its capacity, as well as the compatibility of cargo loading conditions and schemes.

When packaging cargo, it is understood that large-sized cargoes are placed in individual transport warehouses without separating them during loading and reloading (boxes, crates, bins), to be loaded into single transport units. This involves placing several large-sized cargoes without dividing them. The package refers to the acceptance of this single purpose in separate locations for single-unit transport, reloading of large-sized cargoes, and using packaged vehicles in separate locations.

The number of individual cargoes (in boxes, crates, bins, etc.) within the package can range from 6 to 8 to 20 to 30 or more.

In this task, the coefficient utilized in the transportation vehicle, denoted as k_m , is employed to determine the number of transport packets $N_{\text{пак}}$, the weight of the transport packet G , and the cargo carrying capacity of the transport vehicle q_ϵ . The significance lies in establishing its relevance to parameters such as q_m for food product characteristics and the parameters of the pallet.

$k_m = \frac{q_m}{q_\epsilon} = \frac{N_{\text{пак}} \cdot G}{q_\epsilon} = \frac{N_{\text{пак}} \cdot (\gamma \cdot V + g)}{q_\epsilon}$. To optimize the placement of food products in refrigerated containers within the transport packet, it is crucial to determine the characteristics of the refrigerated containers and the appearance of food products. This involves finding the optimal number $N_{\text{пак}}$ and weight G of refrigerated containers for the task, considering their maximum capacity at the highest altitude.

$$q_m = f(G, N_{\text{пак}}) \rightarrow \max, \quad (2)$$

We determine the overlaying in a limited height and identify its technical operation:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \gamma \cdot V_n + g &\leq P_n \\ N_{\text{пак}} \cdot (\gamma \cdot V_n + g) &\leq q_\epsilon \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (3)$$

Here, G - represents the weight of the transport packet, in kilograms:

$$G = j \cdot V_n \leq P_n, \quad (4)$$

Here, γ denotes the density, in kilograms per cubic meter (kg/m^3), and V_n represents the useful volume for placing the transport packet, measured in cubic meters (m^3):

$$V_n = a \cdot b \cdot h \cdot K_n, \quad (5)$$

Here, g - represents the weight of the transport packet itself, measured in kilograms (kg).

P_n - represents the cargo carrying capacity of the transport packet, also measured in kilograms (kg).

a - represents the length of the transport packet, measured in millimeters (mm).

b - represents the width of the transport packet, measured in millimeters (mm).

h - represents the height of the transport packet, measured in millimeters (mm).

K_n - represents the calculation coefficient of the pallet.

The parameters of the refrigerated container and the transport packet are given in the second clause according to mathematical relations. To determine the number of various loads that can be placed in a single transport container, they can be found using the following approach.

$$N_{max}^1 = \left\{ \frac{L}{b + \lambda} \right\} \cdot \left\{ \frac{B}{a + \lambda} \right\} \cdot \left\{ \frac{H}{h} \right\}, \quad (6)$$

or

$$N_{max}^2 = \left\{ \frac{L}{a + \lambda} \right\} \cdot \left\{ \frac{B}{b + \lambda} \right\} \cdot \left\{ \frac{H}{h} \right\}, \quad (7)$$

Here:

L - represents the length of the refrigerated container, measured in meters (m).

B - represents the width of the refrigerated container, measured in meters (m).

H - represents the height of the refrigerated container, measured in meters (m).

λ - represents the technical condition opening between package rows.

Conclusion

In the research findings, it is proposed to ensure the transportation of goods at a specified temperature range using refrigerated containers and pallets, and the air temperature for delivery is consistently distributed throughout the container volume at each point. The main factors determining the correct type of pallet are the volume and weight of the transported cargo, the shipping characteristics, and the required temperature. Overcoming the air cargo compartmentation in refrigerated containers is addressed. Consideration is given to the number, volume, and location of the pallets in accordance with the proposed measurements based on the product's characteristics. Variants for determining the number of different loads that can be placed from a single transport capacity have been developed. The utilization of a coefficient in the transport capacity, as described in the requirements, helps to determine the number of transport packets in the transport capacity.

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